

BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM: APPLYING ICT TO OPEN BUILDING AND MASS HOUSING

Madrazo, Leandro; Cojo, Angel Martin; Sicilia, Álvaro & Costa, Gonçal

ARC Enginyeria i Arquitectura La Salle
Universitat Ramón Llull
Barcelona, SPAIN

ABSTRACT

BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM is a computer-supported housing design and building system which adheres to the principles of open building in two ways: by distinguishing between support and infill systems, and by enabling the participation of different actors in the processes of designing, building and using the dwellings. A rule-based generative system creates the housing units automatically and stores them in the system's database. Optimization techniques are used to assemble the units into housing buildings which can be constructed in multiple ways using industrial components stored in a catalogue. The different actors (architects, users, manufacturers, builders) participate at the different stages of the design process, interacting with and through the system.

Keywords: Open Building, User Participation, Mass Customization, Collaborative Design

INTRODUCTION

The concept of Open Building stems from the theories developed by Habraken and the SAR around forty years ago (Habraken 1972, 1976), in particular from the distinction between supports and infill systems. According to those theories, a support is a structure that accommodates a multiplicity of housing units, which in turn make up the infill. Both of them –support and infill– are independent systems, although they are strongly interrelated. More important than the physical distinction between both systems –as supporting skeleton and as housing unit– is the fact that each delimits a specific decision-making sphere in the design and construction process of mass housing. Hence, the support is the collective domain controlled by the community, whereas the infill is the private domain in command of the individual household. This twofold nature of the support, as a material structure and as an abstract space of control, characterizes the original formulation of Habraken’s theories. The ultimate purpose of Habraken’s approach was to bring the individual user back in the design and building process of mass housing: by ascribing a specific realm in the decision-making process to the individual user – the infill– he or she could participate in the creation of a dwelling.

As formulated by Kendall and Teicher (2000), Open Building (OB) is based on three key concepts adopted from Habraken’s theories: levels, supports and infill. Firstly, OB acknowledges that decision-making is distributed among different levels –technical, aesthetic, financial and social– where different professionals intervene in the process of the design, construction, occupation and lifetime of the building. A support is then defined as “the permanent, shared part of a building which provides serviced space for occupancy” (p. 32), while infill “represents a relatively mutable part of the building” (p. 4). Building upon these concepts, the aim of OB is to lend a “formal structure to traditional and inherent levels of environmental decision-making, while offering design methods based on the new insights and supported by current applied research” (p. 6).

THE SYSTEM APPROACH TO THE BUILT ENVIRONMENT

Habraken’s theory of supports is an example of the systems approach to the built environment that emerged during the 1960s and 1970s. As Fergusson (1975) explained, at that time the application of system theory to architecture and urban planning was “stimulated by the obvious need and desire to improve design and planning decisions”, as well as by the need “to justify decisions once they have been made” to the various participants involved in the design process –such as individual clients as well as corporate bodies, community representatives and building committees– who had diverse interests and objectives with regard to particular urban or architectural problem. According to Fergusson, the system approach is based on two main principles: holism, a perception of the relatedness of things in approaching reality or a problem, and rationality, applying methods and procedures to problem-solving.

The holistic view in Habraken’s theory of supports is manifest in understanding the building as the result of a complex decision-making process in which different experts participate. From this complex reality, Habraken derives an abstract model composed of supports and infill. As Fergusson contended, in system theory the concepts of “model” and “system” are inextricably interrelated: “the system one constructs is formulated in terms of a model and, conversely, the model is usually that of a system” (p. 18) Based on this abstract model, Habraken elaborates an analytic method to analyze –rather than to design– the interrelations between support and infill systems which represents the

rational component of his system approach to housing design. The starting point of this method is the organization of the spatial structure of a support system in zones. Then, a dwelling unit is made up of sectors, that is, of aggregations of areas located at different zones. The intrinsic limitations of the physical components of the support system – building services, structural components– constrain the position and size of the dwelling units. By the same token, the standards applied to living spaces –minimum sizes, illumination– and the functional requirements –furniture, kitchen and bathroom fixtures– impose limitations on the configuration of the dwelling spaces. In this way, through an understanding of the rules inherent to systems and their multiple interrelationships, a method to analyze and evaluate alternatives of both support and infill systems is then formulated.

Habraken's method epitomizes the distinction between building systems and systems building (Fergusson 1975). The former refers to "an assembly of building subsystems and components, and the rules for putting them together in a building" (p. 62). Systems building, on the other hand, has to do with "the application of the systems approach to construction, normally resulting in the organization of programming, planning, design, financing, manufacturing, construction, and evaluation of buildings under single, or highly coordinated, management into an efficient total process" (p. 62). With building systems, for example, it is possible to achieve better management by producing building components in the factory, whereas with systems building, "the architect is not simply incorporating new technology; he is asking society to transform radically its economic organization so as to provide shelter more efficiently" (p. 69). Habraken's theory of support and infill, therefore, is an example of systems building applied to housing design.

BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM

The objective of BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM is to integrate ICT in the design and construction of collective housing in line with the principles of open building. The system started to be developed in 2002, and the first prototype was completed in 2005. The early version was a rule-based system which made it possible to generate housing units and blocks by means of a stand-alone application (Madrado & Sicilia 2005). The development of the prototype conveyed both the design of a housing system as well as a generative system that automatically generates the variations of housing units and blocks. Afterwards, a grant from the Spanish 2005-2008 National RDI plan allowed us to develop a complete new system after the experience gained with the prototype, a comprehensive on-line environment that would facilitate interaction between the different actors involved in the design and building process.

SYSTEM STRUCTURE

BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM is based on holistic view of housing building, which encompasses a comprehensive building model based on the distinction between support and infill, building subsystems –spatial layout, structure, building services and envelope– and building components defined and stored in the system's catalogue. It embodies both building systems and systems building approaches insofar as it integrates industrialized building components within an overall system which regulates the design, construction and use of the building.

Figure 1: Structure of the system.

The structure of the system is composed of three layers (Fig. 1). The lowest level describes the specific conditions of the building components that will be used in the housing design and construction, such as the orientation of the site, the building components or the material to be used in the structure. The intermediate level contains the information on four building subsystems: spatial, structure, building services and envelope. At the top level, the system regulates the relations between subsystems by setting up the rules by which elements from different subsystems can interact with each other.

At the outset, there is a clear separation in this structure between the generic, abstract system components (support structure, rules of assembly, dimensional coordination and rules of transformation) and the specific components for each building subsystem. This separation guarantees the versatility and adaptability of the housing produced by the system, enabling a design to be materialized in various forms using multiple combinations of building components from different manufacturers. This disentangling of building systems conforms to the principles of open building (Kendall & Teicher, 2000, p. 47).

SYSTEM COMPONENTS

Support structure

Housing units are based on a spatial structure made of horizontal bands and vertical bars placed over a modular grid (Fig. 2). A similar division of floor plans into bands or zones was already considered by Habraken in his seminal work. Maximum and minimum dimensions are established for each of the bands. For instance, the intermediate areas Z2 and Z4 can vary from 2.4 to 3.6 meters. These thresholds guarantee that the rooms placed within these zones (e.g., dining and living rooms, bedrooms) will have the right size. This is an example of the way in which a priori principles (e.g., a spatial structure made up of vertical bars and horizontal bands) and conditions imposed by a subsystem (e.g., Spatial Layout subsystem) are built into the system. This interweaving of support and infill systems makes it possible to

automatically generate housing designs according to the rules built into the system, a unique feature of our project that distinguishes it from previous works.

Figure 2: Support structure divided in bands and bars

At the intersection of a horizontal band and a vertical bar lies a cell, the minimum spatial unit with a function. Some of the attributes of a cell (function, maximum and minimum dimensions) are determined by its location within the structure of horizontal bands and vertical bars (see Spatial Layout subsystem). This underlying spatial structure based on the grouping of cells –which belong to both a band and a bar– into rooms distinguishes our approach from the one adopted by Habraken. In fact, this division of the space of the support structure into cells is necessary in order to model the procedure which generates the floor plans automatically based on the spatial relations embedded in a graph and complemented with lists of constraints and aggregation rules (Madrazo et al. 2009).

This spatial structure is the expression of an abstract support system whose purpose is to ensure that the dwelling units that it accommodates will fulfill the functional requirements imposed by the structure, circulation and building services (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Support and infill systems

Rules of assembly

The materialization of an abstract spatial configuration into a building made up of building components is regulated by the system “connectors”. A connector is an element of a subsystem (typically, a structural element and/or a block of building services) which

embodies methods that regulate the interactions with the elements of different subsystems (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Relationships between subsystems within a connector

The resulting grid of connectors is an expression of a “material” rather than an “abstract” support structure made up of structural elements and building services (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Connectors placed on a floor plan

Dimensional coordination

A spatial 1.20 m. grid (4 x 0.30 m) regulates the relationships between the façade, the internal partitions, the structural elements and the building services. Columns can occupy the grid points at will, and their form and dimensions can vary depending on the height of the building, the material of the structure and the dimension of the cantilevers. The façade elements, on the other hand, occupy all the grid cells and their form and dimensions are more homogeneous than those of the structural elements. The internal partitions are placed in a 0.30 cm. grid. (Fig. 6)

Figure 6: Grids, zones and partitions.

Rules of transformation

The location of the partitions is regulated by the grid and by the Spatial Layout subsystem. A specific type of partition is assigned to each qualified area of the support structure (Fig. 7). Thus, the serving zones (Z1, Z3 and Z5), where the less flexible spaces are located, require fixed partitions while the intermediate zones (Z2, Z4), which contain the most flexible spaces, require mobile and dismantlable divisions.

The infill system includes four different kinds of partitions with regard to the degree of transformability of a space over time:

- Fixed elements: To be used in those spaces which are likely to remain unchanged over the building's lifetime (e.g., bathrooms, dwelling divisions).
- Dismountable elements: To be used in spaces which can vary on a middle-term basis (e.g., bedrooms)
- Mobile elements: To separate spaces that change often, even on a daily basis (e.g., the separation between a working area and a bedroom)
- Auxiliary elements: To be used as mobile partitions (e.g., sliding doors) or as space-filtering elements (e.g., a shelf)

Figure 7: Different kinds of partitions

By considering the partitions at both the support and infill levels, it is possible to create “flexible housings” (Schneider & Till 2007) both at the design stage –when the future tenant can explore different alternatives of the housing layout in interaction with the system– and afterwards, when the dwelling is occupied, by easily transforming the space delimiting boundaries.

SUBSYSTEMS

After having described the basic abstract principles that make the system, we will briefly describe each of the four subsystems: Spatial Layout, Structure, Building Services and Envelope.

Spatial Layout Subsystem

The Spatial Layout subsystem consists of all the components and rules to generate floor plans and housing buildings (blocks, towers) resulting from the aggregation of housing units. In order to generate a floor plan, cells placed at the bands and bars of the spatial grid are grouped into rooms, which in turn are assembled to create a dwelling. A generative procedure ensures that the aggregation of cells gives rise to rooms having appropriate dimensions and functions. Likewise, the procedure ensures that a group of rooms makes a functional dwelling by checking the constraints and the adjacency rules. The procedure generates floor plans in a batch mode and stores them in the system database. The floor plans that result from the application of the generative processes can have a width of between 3.6 and 10.2 m. and a depth of between 8 and 12 meters (Fig. 8). Over 10.000 different floor plans have been automatically generated and stored in the system

Figure 8: Housing layouts sharing the same spatial structure

Structure Subsystem

This subsystem encompasses the structural elements (excluding the foundations) and the procedures to determine their positioning and pre-dimensioning. The 'connectors' created by the system for each particular building embody the information about the structural requirements which will call for a different structural solution depending on the materials and dimensional and load-bearing constraints of the structural elements.

All possible structures conform to a unique structural model composed of frames placed at the façades, shear walls and rigid slabs (Fig. 9). Structural elements are not flexible elements in a building. Therefore, they should be attached to elements or zones with low flexibility like circulation cores, service zones, façades and ducts. Shear walls are placed in the circulation core envelop, and structural frames can be aligned to three horizontal service zones (Z1, Z3 and Z5).

Figure 9: Structural and building services model

Building Services Subsystem

This subsystem encompasses the supply (water, electricity, telecommunications) and evacuation (waste water, air, fumes) services of the building. Services are located in a gallery at the base of the building or underground, from which ducts and pipes run upwards through vertical conducts (Fig. 10). The location of the vertical conducts is defined by the information on the connectors, just as it was for the structural elements. Therefore, the building services are planned in close relation with the other subsystems, spatial layout, structure and envelope.

The spatial configuration based the vertical bars and the horizontal bands determines the position of the ducts that deliver building utilities. According to this spatial structure, service wells can be placed at each horizontal band (Fig. 11). The wells are sized to allocate all ducts (supply, exhaust, sewage pipes). The dimension of the well takes into account the spatial grid module as well as the size of the columns. The largest dimension (120 cm.) corresponds to the width of a water closet. This is also the size of the Z1, Z3 and Z5 zones. The smallest dimension (40 cm.) matches the maximum size of the standard column. The inner size of the service well is the result of subtracting the dimension of the column.

Figures 10 and 11: Location of service wells in the zones.

Envelope Subsystem

The envelope subsystem encompasses the outer and inner surfaces that surround the interior space and the building, respectively. Inner partitions also adhere to the 1.20 m. grid. Most of the industrialized products used to create the partitions can adapt to this modular dimension. A variety of partitions, with different materials, thickness and performance levels, can be used to make the fixed and mobile divisions.

The design criteria for the elements making up the external envelopes (Fig. 12) are the following:

- A light façade composed of three layers: exterior, core and interior. The outer cladding is made of light plates of different materials: clay, fiber cement, metal, stoneware, synthetic composites and others.
- Windows and exterior doors are a mixed product made of timber and aluminum.
- The flat roof is constructed with a built-up system which provides a good thermal behavior and simplifies maintenance.
- Internal divisions and ceilings are built with plaster boards and light steel profiles.

Figure 12: External envelopes for different building types.

WORKING SPACES AND LEVELS OF DECISION-MAKING

The computer-based environment of BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM consists of interwoven workspaces where different actors (architects, developers, manufacturers, occupants) participate in a synchronous and asynchronous manner through a distributed process of designing and constructing collective housing projects (Fig. 12). Each of these workspaces represents a level of decision-making where different actors intervene in the design and building process in interaction with the system and each other.

Figure 12: Structure of the working environments.

The system workspaces and their functionalities are the following:

Project development

In this workspace, developers, architects and building managers specify site properties (area, size), number and type of housing units, building and planning regulations (building volumes and height) and environmental conditions (climate, orientation). Alternative solutions for buildings (massing, location) can then be explored for the given site conditions and brief.

Housing unit layouts

In this space, architects select a set of units that will be used later to generate a building among those contained in the system. Searching for housing units in the system database becomes a “discovery” process. Should an adequate layout not be found among the existing solutions, the architect can invoke the generative process to create alternative layouts that conform to the desired criteria (area, number of rooms, number of bathrooms, open or closed kitchen), which then will be stored in the system.

Housing unit configuration

The occupants describe the characteristics of the dwelling (number of occupants and rooms, lifestyles, room interrelationships) by interacting with the system through a sequence of user-friendly interfaces that represent the dwellings in a graphic language that can be understood by laypeople with no knowledge of the conventions of architectural representation, using non-dimensional plans and diagrams as well as photographs (Fig. 13).

Figure 13. Interfaces to define dwelling characteristics

The sequence of interactions is structured in such a way that the information acquired in one interface becomes an input for the next. Following the information collected from different users, a process of generation is prompted to assemble the housing units in a building. Then, after each housing unit has its place in the building, users interact with the architect in a 3d interface which enables them to choose finishes and partitions selecting components from the system's library.

Assembly of housing units' assembly

In this workspace, the architect defines the design criteria for the assembly of living units, for instance: degree of compactness of the housing block; degree of optimization of building services; minimum distances to access cores (staircases, elevators); material of the structural skeleton, and so on. Once the design values are set, a generative process creates the solutions that meet these criteria.

Catalogue of building components

The online catalogue allows manufacturers of various products enter descriptions of their components, using templates which include 3-D models of type components. The components can be introduced into the catalogue through an interactive interface or via external forms in XML format.

This structure of autonomous and interrelated workspaces supports open and non-linear design and construction processes. In order to interact with the system, it is not necessary to proceed along the workspaces in a linear fashion: the workflow through the workspaces can start at different points and at different times. The only prerequisite is to start the Project Development workspace by describing the characteristics of the program (site, brief) and registering the users who will participate in the process. All other spaces can be activated later at any time during the project lifecycle. In this way, the system can support non-linear design and construction processes by exploiting, as Kalay (2004) has argued, the potential of ICT technologies to transform established design and construction practices. For example, the system can support the creation of a network of small interconnected companies collaborating in the construction process (Worst 2007).

CONCLUSIONS

BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM adheres to the systems building approach to architecture insofar as considers the building a complex whole which is the result of procedures that embody the design rules. It also supports a buildings system approach insofar as it operates with industrially produced building components which are part of the system. Likewise, it shares some of the basic ideas of open building, in particular the distinction between support and infill and the need to integrate the different levels of decision-making in the design process. The structure based on differentiated workspaces fosters the participation of different actors at different levels of the design and building process. Altogether, the system exemplifies one way to use ICT to support the principles of open building.

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